

Paper ID

Smart Transport Infrastructures Classification

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Abstract

The adoption of Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) represents a significant paradigm shift in mobility. To navigate this transition effectively, the establishment of standardized procedures for evaluating infrastructure capabilities supporting CCAM is crucial. One of these procedures is the definition of classification schemes to evaluate the maturity, readiness, and support infrastructures can provide for CCAM. These classifications serve a multifaceted purpose, including informing end-users, assisting operators, and aiding authorities and policymakers in planning the evolution of CCAM. Furthermore, as smart infrastructures become more prevalent, these standardized approaches play a pivotal role in infrastructure management, by guiding the planning of future infrastructure improvements and investments to support higher levels of automation and more advanced use cases. Benefiting from early works of infrastructure classifications, mainly focused on the road and automated driving, the H2020 EU funded project TANGENT proposes a Smart Infrastructure Classification Index (SICI) that extends to multimodal transport networks.

Keywords: Smart Infrastructures, Multimodal Transport, Urban and Peri-urban Mobility

Introduction

As the introduction of connected and automated vehicles becomes feasible, public authorities, mobility planners and transport managers need to prepare for the revolution that Connected Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) brings to the transportation sector. Understanding the challenges of traffic safety, efficiency and sustainability that CCAM brings is fundamental to plan, design and implement this new transportation ecosystem. While most early debates were centred on vehicles, it became evident that the infrastructure will have a paramount role. The future transport ecosystem, especially in the urban and peri-urban context, will become a vehicle-infrastructure collaborative smart system. With information on most elements in the smart CCAM system available (vehicles, users, infrastructure, roads, routes, lines, stations, stops, weather, etc.), it will be possible to greatly optimize existing operations and plan smart CCAM systems from scratch, achieving currently unimaginable levels of efficiency and safety.

The TANGENT project [1] is a H2020 EU funded initiative exploring Dynamic Management of Multimodal

Traffic in four European cities (Athens, Manchester, Lisbon, and Rennes), by creating and trialling a Simulation powered Next-Generation Traffic Management System (the TANGENT Tool). The Smart Infrastructure Classification Index (SICI) presented here was created in the context of the TANGENT project, as an instrument to evaluate the maturity of the Smart Transportation Infrastructures in a Multimodal, Urban and Peri-urban context. The project is implementing the automatic calculation of SICI parameters at the TANGENT tool Dashboard and will test it at its case study cities.

CCAM transition

During the transition to CCAM, there will be simultaneous operation of conventional vehicles, connected vehicles and vehicles with different levels of automation, all sharing the same infrastructures and with evolving penetration rates. Several institutions, such as the *European Road Transport Research Advisory Council* (ERTRAC) or the *European Automobile Manufacturers Association* (ACEA) have proposed roadmaps for the deployment of automated driving in the European Union (EU) [2][3], contemplating amongst a myriad of aspects the necessary infrastructure rollouts. In 2021, the International Road Federation (IRF) published a manifesto stating there is a lack of clear system design and classification of Connected and Automated Driving systems, which is hindering the industrialization and usage of CCAM technologies. They consider it is essential to assess the level of infrastructure support and that it is urgent to develop a uniform classification index harmonized worldwide. [4]. Several projects have been evaluating the road infrastructure and vehicle readiness for CCAM. In 2022, the *CCAM Partnership*, a public-private initiative co-funded under the Horizon Europe (HE) programme published its 2021-2027 strategic agenda, which aggregates Research and Innovation (R&I) actions into seven operational clusters. Cluster 4 – “Integrating the vehicle in the transport system” dwells into the Physical and Digital Infrastructure and one of its expected outcomes is the classification of infrastructure support levels and the contribution for an EU-wide/global infrastructure classification harmonization [5].

Road Infrastructure and Automation

Traditionally, the road was considered as an asphalt transportation corridor, composed of roadways and lanes space, its pavement, and the physical elements that regulated its usage (e.g., road signs, road markings). With the massification of electronics, the physical elements list kept being extended to include a myriad of sensors, variable road signs, and all the equipment that comprises the road communication infrastructure. These elements produce digital information that supports digital representations of the road environment which can benefit Connected Vehicles (CVs), Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) and advanced Traffic Management Systems (TMS) [7]. These two dimensions of the road infrastructure are designated the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI). Advanced traffic management functions, such as the ones providing active guidance and traffic control, highly depend on the PDI, but also require the continuous interaction with external stakeholders (e.g., Transport Authorities, Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), mobility cloud service providers) and constitute what has been defined as the Operational Road Infrastructure [7]. To be able to support connectivity and automation one should consider the road infrastructure in three dimensions:

- **Physical road infrastructure:** integration of all the physical elements present where vehicles circulate, namely: (i) Roadways, and other lanes; (ii) Bridges, tunnels, etc.; (iii) Pavement; (iv) Lighting; (v) Safety barriers; (vi) Landmarks, (vii) Pavement markings (viii) Road signs - static and variable, e.g., Dynamic Message Signs (DMS), Variable Message Signs (VMS); (ix) Traffic Control Devices (TCD); (x) Traffic sensors (e.g., radar, lidar, vision systems, loop detectors, ultrasonic, treadles and other counters); (xi) Environmental sensors (e.g., weather, air quality) (xii) Communication infrastructure (e.g., Cooperative Intelligent Transport System (C-ITS)) Roadside Units (RSUs), cellular equipment, fibre back-bone); (xiii) Power infrastructure.
- **Digital road infrastructure:** integration of multiple geo-located information layers containing: (i) *Static data:* Base Maps (e.g., digital cartographic data, topological data, road facilities and technical characteristics, High Definition (HD) maps); (ii) *Semi-static data:* Planned activities and Forecasts (e.g., traffic regulations, road works); (iii) *Semi-dynamic data:* Incidents Information (e.g., accidents, congestion, localized weather events); (iv) *Dynamic data:* Microscopic Traffic Information (e.g., C-ITS data, surrounding vehicles, average speeds, presence of Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs)).
- **Operational road infrastructure:** advanced traffic management functions, which facilitate the traffic flow by providing guidance and/or control and that require integration with external stakeholders' cloud services for added information, such as other modes of transport real-time data (e.g., navigation systems, real-time traffic, incidents reporting, road weather services, tolling systems). Examples of these advanced traffic management functions include: (i) Incident management; (ii) Ramp metering; (iii) Traffic-responsive or traffic-adaptive traffic signal operations; (iv) Active traffic management (e.g., lane merging or overtaking support); (v) Managed lanes; (vi) Integrated corridor management.

Only by simultaneously considering and improving these three infrastructure dimensions, connected and automated mobility can be taken to higher levels of automation. Together they can support a broad variety of use cases, either by direct infrastructure-vehicle interaction (e.g., lane merging, overtaking), by advanced traffic management measures (e.g., vehicle platooning) or by the support of maintenance activities (e.g., HD maps update). To support advanced CCAM use cases, one needs to adapt the physical infrastructure; to sensorize it, in order to have the correct digital representation; to implement suitable communications channels, to provide quality data; and to setup advanced TMS functions. Since the road infrastructure requirements are strongly use case specific, a harmonized approach on how to describe them is highly beneficial. A common understanding of the physical, digital, and operational infrastructures, their specifications, its interfaces, alongside extensive piloting is essential to fulfil the requirements of future CCAM.

State-of-the-Art of Smart Infrastructure Classification

Initial approaches to road classification systems were focused on motorized vehicles driven by humans, mainly communicating the character of service, by describing the road's context (e.g., rural, suburban, urban) and functional type (e.g., motorway, arterial, local).

Since 2018, several new road classification schemes focusing on CCAM capabilities have been proposed.

The first known classification index proposed was the *Infrastructure Support for Automated Driving* (ISAD) developed under the INFRAMIX EU project [8] which assesses the digital and connectivity readiness of the infrastructure to support automated driving. The ISAD index has 5 levels (level E to A) according to the digital information, that is relevant for automated driving, that the infrastructure provides to its users and depending on the connectivity of the infrastructure[8][9]. The lower level of ISAD is E, describing a conventional infrastructure with no AV support or digital information. The highest level is A with an infrastructure supporting cooperative driving where it adds to level C's full set of static and dynamic road information and level B's cooperative perception (real-time information about all vehicles and traffic elements) the ability to guide AVs to optimize the overall traffic flow. Subsequent work in ISAD by the INFRAMIX project refined the 5 levels with concepts such as HD Maps and connectivity considerations [8]. Figure 1 illustrates an example of applying the ISAD classification to a given transport network area.

Figure 1 - ISAD classification of a given transport network area example, from [12]

The US NCHRP-funded project - CRCS, conducted by the Texas A&M Transportation Institute proposed, in 2019, the *Connected Roads Classification System* (CRCS) for the American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) Committee on Agency Administration [10]. This classification scheme is based on three infrastructure dimensions to support CCAM: (1) **Tx: Talking to the Road** (ability to support vehicles to connect to the infrastructure and other vehicles), (2) **Sx: Seeing the Road** (ability to support operation of Automated Driving Systems (ADS) / AVs by providing good physical markings/signage and digital descriptions of the road), and (3) **Mx: Simplifying the Road** (ability to support safety automation and operation by providing suitable Operational Design Domains - ODDs). The CRCS levels assess the maturity of the infrastructure and its need to incorporate new knowledge to meet present and future CCAM requirements. Infrastructure Owners and/or Operators, by describing their infrastructure elements, can characterize their capabilities on the three infrastructure dimensions. Each dimension is evaluated between 1 (needs upgrade and maintenance) and 4 (meets next decade market), yielding three resulting values **Tx**, **Sx** and **Mx** that classify the infrastructure readiness to support CV and AVs.

The *European Asphalt Pavement Association* (EAPA) proposed in 2020 a classification of *Road Readiness for adopting Connected and Automated Vehicles*, which results mostly from the combination of the ISAD and SAE automation levels [11] but also including some parameters characterizing the physical road

infrastructure. This classification framework is intended to classify road sections, aiming at providing the road user with information about the available technologies supporting automated and electrified driving [12]. However, this classification does not consider the quality of the geometric design of the road segments for its automatic recognition, essential for automated driving. To address this the HERG group proposed the concept of *Level of Service of Automated Driving* (LOSAD) which summarizes the physical roadway readiness for automated driving [13]. characterizing how the quality of the roads’ geometric design affects roadway automatic recognition, essential for automated driving. The LOSAD classification scheme has 5 levels, where A – the highest corresponds to operation road sections continuity to ensure automation for SAE level 4-5 and minimum automation disengagements for SAE levels 2-4 - up to level E, where the amount of road sections where automation is possible is so small (or even non-existent) that automation is not recommended.

In 2021, the World Road Association (PIARC) presented its classification scheme – the *Smart Road Classification* (SRC) [14] which combines the PDI automation readiness classification provided by LOSAD, and the infrastructure support in terms of connectivity and digital information provided by ISAD, into a 2D road classification scheme. SRC is composed of five Smart Road Levels of increasing automation, the first being a “**Humanway**” and the latest being an “**Autonomousway**”. Figure 2 presents the diamond chart representation of the SRC.

Figure 2 - Smart Road Classification (SCR) scheme, diamond chart representation, from [14]

This type of visualization allows to easily follow the evolution of the road. The smart road levels improvement is represented in a bottom-to-top approach. Its horizontal axes have percentage scales for the ISAD and LOSAD levels, corresponding to the cumulative percentage each level as of the road facility (e.g., ISAD A ~0%, (...), ISAD E ~80%, LOSAD A ~ 5%, (...), LOSAD E ~30%). These percentages will dramatically evolve over time, changing the diamond shapes and sizes of each SRC level, creating an impactful visualization of the smart levels’ distribution. SRC also introduced an alternative detailed classification system that is organized into four categories (Physical infrastructure, Digital infrastructure,

Connectivity and Users) using the same classification regarding automation from “**Humanway**” to “**Autonomousway**”, fully described in [14].

Although the previous schemes constitute the main existing smart infrastructure classifications, other initiatives should also be referenced, namely [15] [16] and [17].

It is noteworthy that none of the analysed smart infrastructure classification indexes addressed multimodality. This oversight is notable given the promising developments of AVs applied in Public and Demand Responsive Transport solutions and that automation efforts are not limited to vehicles traveling on roads but also apply to rail, water and airways. Additionally, many of the existing classifications do not cover urban environments adequately and can be biased towards higher-speed roads. Thus, a more holistic approach is necessary.

TANGENT Smart Infrastructure Classification Index v1.0

The *Smart Infrastructure Classification Index* (SICI) was devised to be an evolving Classification Index for which future versions can be produced. Here we present its first version (v1.0).

Its focus is on Smart Transport Infrastructure and the Digital information it can provide to vehicles (common, connected, automated), drivers and passengers. It extends the coverage in existing indexes from the road into rail stations and other infrastructure elements in a multimodal network, covering both autonomous vehicles and connected users in these networks.

Existing classifications, like ISAD, define levels of automation and connectivity capability for roads. Lower levels typically apply to conventional roads while higher levels apply to increasingly connected roads and roads better supporting automated vehicles. This is not aligned with the current perspective from autonomous vehicle makers and operators. The autonomous vehicle industry is still pursuing autonomy as a vehicle centred capability, gathering needed information mostly from the vehicle’s own sensors. This is justified by the need for full local decision-making abilities in AVs, especially considering the absolute time-sensitivity involved. Adding to this capability, extended connected services can in fact optimise the experience with extended knowledge about the surroundings. But from the perspective of AV makers and operators this should be primarily supported by services controlled by AV makers and operators. Our perspective with SICI is thus that one key category for the support of AVs needs to focus the physical aspects of the infrastructure such as signage and lighting which AV sensors can use. On top of this key category, other categories add knowledge, safety, and efficiency in a cooperative fashion. Cooperation enhances the AV, CV and legacy vehicles experience to provide an optimisation level that goes beyond what AV makers and operators can provide on their own. To materialize this, SICI uses six distinct categories comprised of a set of measurable evaluation criteria. Each of these criteria result in a single percentual value so a single score for each category can be calculated also as a percentual value. The six categories considered for SICI are:

Category C1 - “Physical Elements”: focuses on the physical infrastructure elements like road marks and signs. These elements are crucial for the perception of human drivers as well by sensors in autonomous vehicles. This category is related with ISAD Level E. It is important to note that autonomous vehicles may operate correctly relying only on elements from this category and this is what is currently happening on motorways around the world. This category evaluates a set of physical element control indexes that are relevant for automated driving,

such as artificial lighting quality, road marks and vertical signage. This category evaluates lighting quality, road marks and vertical signage through technical criteria such as the illumination value or the retroreflection index, calculating the percentage of the network that is above the minimum values for each technical criterion.

Category C2 - “Infrastructure Perception”: The first layer of a smart system is usually perception. In the case of smart road and rail infrastructure this is true. SICI’s 2nd category focuses on the perception layer that is comprised of several different types of sensors which allow monitoring and capturing different aspects such as flow (of vehicles, fleets, and passengers) and safety (detecting incidents, monitoring the weather, etc.). This category evaluates the existence and coverage of a set of equipment types such as video cameras, traffic sensors, radars and LiDARs, train presence detectors, ticketing and passenger control systems, weather/environmental stations, etc. The mere existence of perception elements doesn’t make Infrastructures smart but is an important step towards intelligence. That is why we introduced this category and followed it with categories where perception is transformed into knowledge and then into management actions.

Category C3 - “Reference Information”: Accurate and detailed reference information about infrastructures is essential for connected and automated vehicles to extend their electronic horizon, to provide details beyond what their sensors can measure, as well as provide information otherwise not available to human drivers. SICI’s 3rd category evaluates the availability of reference information on the infrastructure side, namely from road and transport operators. It can also consider such information from third parties, not affiliated with the infrastructure itself, but this should be explicitly mentioned in the SICI report justifying a SICI score. This category evaluates a set of reference information types such as infrastructure geometry and spatial data, HD maps of the infrastructure, lines and schedules, communication infrastructure coverage or sensor calibration data. This reference information should not only exist but be disseminated through at least one channel from SICI category C5 to be considered when evaluating its existence.

Category C4 - “Dynamic Information”: SICI’s 4th category refers to (quasi) real-time information on the transport network state. This category addresses data that changes quickly and is usually produced by perception elements such as those listed in SICI category C2. Knowledge is either extracted directly by the perception sensors, such as in traffic counters, computed, such as in passenger control systems, or results from human or artificial intelligence analysis of the sensor data collected, such as in video cameras or 3D LiDAR. Furthermore, elements of dynamic information can also be used for further analysis, to produce even more relevant dynamic information (such as incident detection or traffic and weather forecasts), namely through forecasting. We consider the resulting information itself, dynamic information also. This category evaluates a set of dynamic information types such as traffic conditions, transport demand, public transport occupation, transport incidents and associated forecasts to all the real-time information types. The evaluation approach is equivalent to the one in C3, evaluating the availability of these types of data throughout the network and considering only cases when the data is available in at least one channel from SICI category C5.

Category C5 - “Information Channels”: Information needs to reach vehicles, drivers and transport passengers, to become valuable. This motivates SICI’s 5th category. The availability of different communication channels defines the ability of smart infrastructure to share information. This category evaluates a set of information

channels such as VMS, public announcement systems, signalling systems, cellular network, V2X Road-Side Units, Datex II National Access Points, RDS-TMC, service providers or vehicle navigation platforms. This category evaluates the coverage of the network by these communication channels.

Category C6 - "Active Traffic Management": Since SICI category C1, we have covered mechanisms that convey information from the infrastructure to the vehicle, driver and/or passenger, except for category 2, which actually collects information from the vehicles, drivers and/or passengers. There is no actual interactivity and bidirectionality in these categories. They build on top of each other a system that can perceive, communicate, know, and share its knowledge. What is lacking here is the ability for this system to adapt and optimise itself through actual the bidirectionality between the smart infrastructure and the (smart) vehicles, drivers and/or passengers. SICI's last category C6 evaluates a set of classic and cooperative active traffic management use cases. Among the classic ones we can count incident detection and management, variable speed limits, train control and signalling, transit signal priority, lane management, dynamic traffic lights, congestion pricing, ramp metering, smart parking or dynamic scheduling and dispatching for public transport. As for the cooperative ones we count speed and gap advice, assisted lane merge and lane change, emergency vehicle priority, cooperative intersection management, platooning, cooperative adaptive cruise control or infrastructure-guided automated driving. The evaluation for this category will identify if these use cases are available throughout the network, naturally producing very low values at the current prototype stage of most of these technologies.

An individual scoring of each SICI category is considered. This is a fundamental concept behind TANGENT'SICI, as the different categories focus on different dimensions of a smart infrastructure, which might correlate but do not cancel each other out. Different stakeholders may value different dimensions and we aim at delivering a comprehensive tool that can benefit most of them. Each category has different evaluation criteria, described in the TANGENT SICI v1.0. All parameters are calculated as a percentage of the infrastructure/network that fulfils a given criteria, ranging from 0 to 100% and an average score for all evaluation elements of each category is obtained, as illustrated in Figure 3. With SICI one can easily compare different infrastructures using this type of criteria representation. The full description of SICI will be made publicly available at TANGENT's deliverable D6.6 - "Smart infrastructure index report" in 2024, including an extensive review of the state of the art, a comprehensive definition of the evaluation criteria for each category and a description of how SICI will be implemented at the TANGENT tool.

Conclusions

The mobility paradigm shift to CCAM is underway. To cope with the multi-stage transition it represents, it is beneficial to have standardized procedures to evaluate the capabilities of infrastructures in supporting this shift, by conveying what is available for end-users, helping operators identify network sections that are not effectively supported, and provide a tool for authorities and policymakers to plan the evolution in CCAM. In addition, when smart infrastructures are a consolidated reality, these standardized taxonomies and classifications can aid in infrastructure management, guide planning future infrastructure improvements and investments and leverage higher SAE levels of automation.

With the first Infrastructure classification index originating in 2018 these have been evolving during the last

six years. The original ISAD classification scheme was designed with motorways in mind, had a single A to E evaluation scale where it evaluated together distinct aspects such as the availability of different types of information, the physical infrastructure, communications and traffic management. Subsequent indexes adopted more structured and multi-dimensional approaches, evaluating different parameters separately and so does SICI. These indexes also introduced the vehicle perspective and mixed it using the SAE automation levels. In SICI we believe the infrastructure evaluation should be agnostic to the vehicle perspective and provide enough information for vehicle, traveller and other transportation entities’ perspectives to be able to make proposer use of the index on their own. This allows vehicles and other transport infrastructure actors to use SICI to independently assess their Operational Design Domain (ODD) and determine optimal operation within the infrastructure. This is an important step when developing an index for the transportation infrastructure sector, and not just for roads or motorways.

Figure 3 – Illustrative example of the comparison of two transport infrastructures using SICI

The SICI v1.0 positions itself as a holistic smart transportation infrastructure classification index, relatively to existing classifications, while trying to keep the evaluation process simple and clear. It introduces six categories of evaluation items: Physical Elements, Infrastructure Perception, Reference Information, Dynamic Information, Information Channels and Active Traffic Management.

The separate evaluation and scoring of these categories are fundamental to the concept behind SICI, as the different categories focus on different dimensions of maturity of a smart infrastructure, which correlate but do not cancel each other out. E.g., evaluating the physical infrastructure aspects alone would be a too narrow approach but considering only connectivity or information availability aspects would also be inadequate.

Additionally, this addresses the fact that different stakeholders have different views on how CCAM should evolve, allowing to evaluate the transport network from different perspectives. Through a harmonized and more comprehensive classification, the SICI can better support the future alignment between different stakeholders. By extending coverage from automated vehicles on roads into the multimodal transportation ecosystem and by defining a dynamical, evolving set of evaluation categories and criteria, SICI is closing gaps in existing Smart Transportation Infrastructure Classification systems and providing support for the evaluation and planning of CCAM support in full-fledged cooperative multimodal transportation systems.

Acknowledgements

The TANGENT project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 955273.

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